

RECYCLING POST-CONSUMER FIBRES FROM WOOD WASTE INTO NEW WOOD-BASED PANELS

MDF

PB

Medium-density fibreboards (MDF) and particleboards (PB) are wood-based panels (WBP), manufactured by combining wood fibres or particles with glue and compressing the mixture under heat. By adjusting the glue formulation and pressing conditions, these boards can be made with different properties, including moisture resistance, fire retardancy and load-bearing capacity.

APPLICATIONS

MDF and PB are widely used in furniture manufacturing, interior design, and construction sector, offering functional and decorative uses in kitchens, offices, bedrooms, and living rooms. When painted, lacquered or laminated, they provide a broad range of aesthetic options.

Their structure is well-suited to industrial processing techniques such as cutting, milling, drilling and finishing, enabling applications for wall cladding, partitions, kitchen cabinetry, shelving, upholstered furniture components, fruit and vegetable packaging, and laminate flooring.

INCORPORATING RECYCLED POST-CONSUMER MDF FIBRES INTO NEW MDF PANELS (DEMO F)

The incorporation of **15% and 25% recycled MDF fibres into new panels was successfully demonstrated at lab scale using fibres from two different technologies**: “modified thermal mechanical pulping (mTMP)” developed by the Dresden Institute for Wood Technology (IHD) and the so called “wet process” by Dieffenbacher.

These fibres are used in the conventional panel production process and the resulting physical and mechanical properties align with industrial reference panels in most points (e.g. bending strength, thickness swelling, stiffness). However, internal bond, panel density and surface quality require some optimisation. Overall, incorporating 15% recycled fibres yielded better performance than 25%.

ONGOING R&D

Industrial trials are foreseen with 15% and 25% recycled fibres aiming to achieve panels that comply with market requirements. Preliminary industrial trials showed promising results and underline the importance of using fibres as clean as possible to achieve the required MDF surface quality when scaling up.

INTEGRATING RECYCLED MDF FINES IN THE SURFACE LAYER OF PB (DEMO D)

When recycling fibreboards, both fibres and fines are obtained, depending on the process used. Fines are substantially shorter than fibres and have been integrated to 10%, 20% and 30% into the surface layer of PB. The fines were produced with the “dry process” developed by Dieffenbacher – a water and chemical-free mechanical process.

Up to 20% substitution, physical and mechanical properties including internal bond, thickness swelling, bending strength, and surface soundness are comparable to reference panels. Additionally, the panels deliver a smoother surface layer. No changes to the gluing process are required if the particle size of the recycling fines is well controlled.

Even a substitution of 30% with post-consumer material showed good results at lab scale. However, the industrial trials will focus on 20% substitution due to potential effects on product performance and process stability. Further optimisation and scale-up tests are ongoing.

ONGOING R&D

Preparations advance for industrial trials with up to 20% recycled fines in PB production. Efforts focus on optimising machinability, ensuring surface quality and compliance with market requirements and product standards.

For both demos, Sonae Arauco is setting operational and safety requirements for the industrial tests, while the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences supports additional lab trials for MDF to optimise testing parameters.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Lab results of the EcoReFibre Project
Demonstrations F and D:

MDF and PB with recycled wood content achieve comparable performance as reference panels.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based and carbon storing material wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer WBPs into production helps close material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. Through horizontal recycling of WBPs, material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life WBPs to be broken down into fibres and particles which are then reintegrated into new panel production. Lab trials have shown that MDF can incorporate up to 25% recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, raw material costs are the main operating expense, and increasing recycled content helps reduce exposure to volatile virgin timber prices and improve profitability. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for Industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular wood-based panel value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP).

IMPACT

As part of its circular bioeconomy efforts, Sonae Arauco currently uses around 30% recycled wood in its total wood input, mainly in particleboard production, where recycled content can go over 70%. Within EcoReFibre, the company focuses on increasing the share of recycled wood and address the technological challenges of incorporating recycled MDF into new panels, and other products across its portfolio.

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

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